

Learning in a Distributed Virtual Community: Initial Findings and Exploratory Analysis

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Abstract: This paper presents findings from a research project that aims to build an understanding of how the informal experience of knowledge contributes to the construction of formal knowledge by producing a “thick description” of the Blender learning ecosystem, articulating its socio-technical landscape, the actors and the networks, based on the trajectories of participation and learning of blenderheads and the researcher’s own experience. Initial exploratory analysis of the semiotic domain, affiliation groups and affiliation spaces and the researcher’s personal learning environment are presented to argue for the advantage of combining different strategies for the mapping of a community and to start characterizing the Blender community.

Introduction

The dawn of the new century brought us a landscape of opportunities and risks where choices and challenges are discernible, both for the present and for the future of our collective path. Understanding that “the internet is the fabric of our lives” (Castells, 2004:15) implies recognizing a future where the “homo sapiens digital” (Prensky, 2009) will be immersed in a more intelligent and cognitive demanding popular culture (Johnson, 2006), participating in communities of “prosumers” (Toffler, 1984) sustained by social networks on the Internet. By sharing a “participatory culture” (Jenkins, 2006), that “homo sapiens digital” (Prensky, 2009) is building the transition from an “industrial information economy” to a “network information economy” (Benkler, 2006), while becoming a thespian of a “collective intelligence” (Levy, 1997). The Net Society (Castells, 2004), a “new social structure based predominantly on networks” (p. 16), calls for the transfiguration of the Information and Communication Technologies into Interaction and Collaboration Technologies, drawing the present scenario where “Billions of people networked together can now actively participate in innovation, wealth creation and social development in a way never before imagined as feasible” (Tapscott & Williams, 2007, p. 11). Faced with such turmoil and vertiginous velocity, waves of uncertainty and of opportunity mingle, revealing the myriad of challenges facing our collective dimension.

Present educational systems are heirs of a design appropriate to the needs of the Industrial Age, they are closely related with an “Industrial information economy” (Benkler, 2006). However, “We are entering a world in which we all will have to acquire new knowledge and skills on an almost continuous basis” (Brown & Adler, 2008, p. 18) and the challenges posed require a redesign that fosters the building of skills that enable us “to acquire the intellectual capacity of learning to learn throughout one’s whole life, retrieving the information that is digitally stored, recombining it, and using it to produce knowledge for whatever purpose we want” (Castells, 2004, p. 320). As stated by Dias (2007), “Communicating and learning in the network are thus aspects of the under way change in the development of education and training for the Knowledge Society” (p. 31). The collective dimension of the Internet (Benkler, 2006; Castells, 2004; Tapscott & Williams, 2007) and the assumption that “The Internet has also fostered a new culture of sharing, one in which content is freely contributed and distributed with few restrictions or costs” (Brown & Adler, 2008, p. 18) presents new needs and opportunities for education. Besides the potential for fostering social learning (Brown & Adler, 2008), the expansion of learner-centered opportunities brought by

collaboration and social networking applications strengthens the need for an approach to learning as a social process that requires “learning to be”, that involves the learner in the building of an identity and in the participation in a practice and a socially constructed domain (Brown, Collins, & Duguid, 1989; among others). This present landscape urges for a redesign of the school system focused on a “demand-pull learning” built upon processes of participation and “based on providing students with access to rich (sometimes virtual) learning communities built around a practice” (Brown & Adler, 2008, p. 30). It drives us to the understanding that “the network of interactions aimed at promoting the activities of participation, sharing and collaboration is the creative environment of the learning contexts” (Dias, 2007, p. 34) and that “It's these distributed and collaborative learning communities that shape the knowledge society” (Dias, 2004, p. 29).

This research acknowledges the fact that “There is no more fundamental restructuring” than of the educational system (Castells, 2004, p. 320). It aims to contribute to a better understanding of the emerging open participatory learning ecosystem (Brown & Adler, 2008), finding in the virtual communities formed within Free/Libre Software and Open Source movements a relevant landscape to help us uncover some of the nuances of learning in the near future, a better understanding of what learning is and might be in the 21st century. These communities already represent a key element of the collaboration economy (Tapscott & Williams, 2007) helping to shape the global landscape. They stand out as one of the most important “flatteners” (Friedman, 2006) and are a present sign that gives us hope for the possibility of an optimistic future (Attali, 2007).

The Study

The research project, developed within a doctoral program in Educational Technology at the University of Minho (Portugal), aims to build an understanding of how the informal experience of knowledge contributes to the construction of formal knowledge. By searching for which characteristics and meanings encompass participation in a distributed virtual community in which people work together voluntarily to develop and maintain Blender ([Http://www.blender.org/](http://www.blender.org/)), a Free/Libre and Open Source software, we intend to produce a “thick description” (Geertz, 1973) of the Blender software learning ecosystem, articulating its socio-technical landscape, the components and their interactions, the actors and the networks, based on the trajectories of participation and learning of “blenderheads” and the researcher’s own experience. We approach this virtual community as an informal, non-formal and formal learning entity with a special focus on sustainability factors, innovation, creation and leadership processes.

The study is an ethnographic one, characterized by starting with a question (Gregory, 2005) or “foreshadowed problems” (Schumacher & McMillan, 1993, p. 408) and the pursuit of the “emic” perspective. The conception of the research process as inductive, the carry out of the research in “natural” settings, and an emergent research design are also Ethnographic characteristics (Gregory, 2005; Schumacher & McMillan, 1993). Although commonly this qualitative research approach is associated with data collection strategies such as participant observation, interviewing and artifact collection (Schumacher & McMillan, 1993), it is possible to combine these strategies with quantitative data (Gregory, 2005), as it is our case. In our study, the immersion in the context is complemented with social network analysis, for example.

According to Patton (1990), “Approaching fieldwork without being constrained by predetermined categories of analysis contributes to the depth, openness, and detail of qualitative inquiry” (p. 13). We have, therefore, built a theoretical framework to guide without constraining the emergent design of the study. This framework encompasses Situated Cognition (Brown, Collins & Duguid, 1989), Communities of Practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991; among others), Connectivism (Siemens, 2005), Personal Learning Environment (Attwell, 2007), Actor-Network Theory (Law, 1992; among others) and Activity Theory (Engeström, 1987). This should not be interpreted as imposing a conceptual framework or bias the fieldwork. Rather, as offering a conceptual lens that facilitates the initial stages of introduction to the community, the access to the field and the exploratory/unstructured data collection and observation.

Findings

During the first months of the study, we focused our efforts on familiarization with the community and on gaining access to the field. This meant not only learning to use the software but mostly characterizing the semiotic domain, the “set of practices that recruits one or more modalities (e.g. oral or written language, images, equations,

symbols, sounds, gestures, graphs, artifacts, etc.) to communicate distinctive types of meanings” (Gee, 2003, p. 18), and mapping the field by identifying the “affinity groups” (Gee, 2003) and the “affinity spaces” (Gee, 2007), where “people bond first and foremost to an endeavor or interest and secondarily, if at all, to each other” (p. 98). During this initial stage, we relied heavily on participant observation, field diary notes and on collecting and analyzing different sets of quantitative data.

Through this first approach to the community, and since the very beginning, we’ve been concerned with tracing our Personal Learning Environment (PLE), based upon a reflexive account of our own Blender learning experiences. For this, we followed the view of Attwel (2007) when describing PLE as “not an application but rather a new approach to the use of new technologies for learning” (p. 5). Since “A PLE is comprised of all the different tools we use in our everyday life for learning” (Attwell, 2007, p. 4), it “can provide more holistic learning environments, bringing together sources and contexts for learning hitherto separate” (p. 5), and might also “include and bring together all learning, including informal learning, workplace learning, learning from the home, learning driven by problem solving and learning motivated by personal interest as well as learning through engagement in formal educational programmes” (p. 4). This view is very close to the portrait drawn by Downes (2005) for what “e-learning 2.0” was starting to look like: “one node in a web of content, connected to other nodes and content creation services used by other students. It becomes, not an institutional or corporate application, but a personal learning center, where content is reused and remixed according to the student’s own needs and interests. It becomes, indeed, not a single application, but a collection of interoperating applications—an environment rather than a system.”

Figure 1: Personal Learning Environment

The diagram is a first draft of this personal trajectory map. It’s an attempt to identify the tools, services and spaces that we’ve used until this moment, grouped according to the European Commission (2001) definitions of formal, non-formal and informal learning: *Formal*: “typically provided by an education or training institution, structured (in terms of learning objectives, learning time or learning support) and leading to certification. Formal learning is intentional from the learner’s perspective” (p. 32); *Non-formal*: “is not provided by an education or training institution and typically does not lead to certification. It is, however, structured (in terms of learning objectives, learning time or learning support). Non-formal learning is intentional from the learner’s perspective” (p. 33); *Informal*: “resulting from daily-life activities related to work, family or leisure. It is not structured (in terms of learning objectives, learning time or learning support) and typically does not lead to certification. Informal learning may be intentional, but in most cases it is non-intentional” (p. 32).

The diagram sums up several of the initiatives, situations and processes that we have been involved in the last months, including distance and face-to-face course attending (i.e. TOSMI 2010), participation in physically “on site” events (Blender Conference 2010 and informal user meetings), artifact exploration and usage (i.e. official DVD tutorials, magazine tutorials, books, manuals, etc.), asynchronous communication (i.e. lurking in forums, posting/replying, web syndication, etc.), synchronous communication (i.e. IRC chat sessions), etc. We took descriptive and reflexive field notes during, or shortly after, all these activities. The following stages will include

field notes analysis and interviews, as well as the continuing of participant observation, and participation in the community daily life and natural settings.

Our effort to characterize the landscape also used quantitative data and statistical analysis. Table 1 highlights part of the data gathered across some of the most popular “affinity spaces”, specifically data from some of the existing public forums totally devoted to Blender software development and use. The presented data refers to May 2008 and October 2010, the release dates of “Big Buck Bunny” and “Sintel”, the two latest Blender Foundation's open movies, two projects and events of great significance to the community that received large press coverage among the 3D animation and Free Software / Open Source software milieu.

The most popular forums, in May 2008 and October 2010, present a percentage growth of 109% and 234% between these two dates. The most popular forum, with nearly 70000 registered members in October 2010, is also the most active and the most appealing. It seems clear the suggestion of an increasing number of newcomers and a community with an ascending life curve.

	Members		Members per day		Posts per day		Topics per day		Posts per topic	
	May-08	Oct-10	May-08	Oct-10	May-08	Oct-10	May-08	Oct-10	May-08	Oct-10
Blender Artists	33476	69994	14.1	21.4	465.8	523.0	51.0	58.8	9.1	8.9
Blender.org	18091	60442	8.8	20.6	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Blend.Polis	3723	6429	1.9	2.3	116.2	125.7	8.8	10.7	13.2	11.8
The Blender Clan	4839	9843	2.8	3.7	94.8	129.8	7.5	10.3	12.7	12.6
Blender3D.cz	527	645	0.4	0.3	33.9	22.2	2.9	2.1	11.5	10.6
Blender.it	4488	6215	3.3	2.8	55.6	52.2	6.1	5.9	9.0	8.8
Polska Strona Blendera	2551	3562	1.9	1.6	19.2	13.2	2.5	1.8	7.6	7.5
G-Blender	13671	14831	10.3	6.7	9.0	6.7	2.2	1.6	4.1	4.3
Blenderowinia	1887	3751	4.1	2.8	52.2	53.7	4.8	4.4	10.9	12.3
Blender Brasil	2704	6180	6.3	4.7	21.8	24.6	4.0	2.9	5.5	8.4
Blender PT	306	1327	0.8	1.0	2.8	4.5	0.4	0.3	7.2	13.1
Blender Underground	330	1245	1.3	1.1	27.3	42.8	2.4	4.1	11.2	10.5
BlenderNewbies	351	2228	1.4	2.0	13.6	27.3	2.3	3.6	5.9	7.5

Table 1: Registered members and publishing activities in Blender Forums 2008-2010

Social network analysis was another strategy used to map the existing actors and networks across the landscape. We created a two-mode sociomatrix to describe the membership or participation of a set of actors in a set of events or organizations. The affiliation data is a set of binary relationships (can assume the value of 0 or 1) that codifies the relations between actors and events or organizations. The relevance of this data can be justified either by the assumption of “Co-Affiliation as Opportunity”, common affiliations create opportunities for social ties, or “Co-Affiliation as Indicator”, common affiliations are an indicator of existing ties (Borgatti & Halgin, in press).

Figure 2: Affiliation Network with Radial Layout

Figure 2 is an affiliation network with 330 nodes and 13 events/organizations. Nodes correspond to actors and ties are the membership or participation in organizations or events. It was created with public data gathered from several sources: individuals credited in the Blender Foundation's open movie projects (Elephants Dream, Sintel and Big Buck Bunny), current list of Blender Foundation Certified Trainers, members of the Blender

Certification Review Board, speakers on the annual Blender Conference from 2004 to 2010, developers currently active. These events and projects are some of the most important initiatives directly promoted by the Blender Foundation, a non-profit public benefit corporation that takes on the responsibility of maintaining and improving the Blender software via a public accessible source code system under the GNU GPL license. In the graph, nodes are positioned onto concentric circles of different radius according to their degree of centrality. Nodes closer to the center, nodes of greater centrality, might be considered more prominent or active. In other words, the actors closer to the center are the ones with a higher degree of affiliation, the ones with a higher level or membership or participation in events or projects promoted by the Blender Foundation. They are more central in a network of either existing or potential social ties.

Currently, we are expanding the amount and data sources to use various metrics and calculate the activity, connectivity and centrality of each node. By combining the results of these social network analysis we aim at identifying the most important or prominent actors and select them for future in depth interviews.

Final thoughts

There are several evidences that strongly suggest that the Blender universe is expanding fast. There are now several new websites and ongoing movie or game projects sustained and initiated by users, running independently from the Blender Foundation. Affiliation spaces like forums and blogs have seen a significant increase of the number of registered members and participants. Blender education and learning as thus become a central concern shared by the Blender Foundation and the users. The Blender Foundation Certified Trainer program, the emergence of several business models invented around the creation and distribution of training materials, the increasing number of training materials and the appearance of distance and face-to-face certified courses are just some of the consequences. It's a dynamic learning environment. There's also an interesting complementarity between the virtual and physical domains, physical acquaintances that occur in face-to-face settings (i.e. courses, user meetings, etc.) overcome the geographical distances by the use of virtual communication devices (i.e. e-mail, forums, VoIP, etc.) and social ties forged from online collaboration or discussions extend to face-to-face interaction.

Free/Libre and Open Source Software and Free Culture are two philosophies or social concerns shared by the vast majority, but not all, of the people in the Blender community. Issues related to these topics are common in news or discussions. This presence seems more visible when related to actors with a considerable past history of participation and engagement. Blender users profiles appear to be considerable heterogeneous, including professionals and hobbyists, people with different backgrounds and occupations (i.e. teachers, scientists, artists, students, etc.), people from all over the world, etc. This heterogeneity is also visible among people engaged in the software development, to which prior computer science education is not required. Nevertheless, it is clear the predominance of artistic oriented male adults.

Our final thoughts are mostly sustained by our ethnographic immersion to date. As so, it is expected that new data and further analysis might confirm or complement some of these thoughts or shed a new light. The combined use of this qualitative data and of social network analysis have showed great potential for mapping the community and members' participation and learning in it.

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